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INTELLIGENT SYSTEMS FOR PERSONAL EQUIPMENT MONITORING

A study of factors affecting on zonation, qualitative and quantitative composition of wireless sensor network elements for microclimate monitoring under clothing space in the system “body - special clothing - environment” in real life setting leads to the concept of the arrangement of elements of wireless sensor network. For the first time a multidisciplinary study of the factors under clothing space was carried out with a view to wireless sensor networks using for the monitoring parameters and impact assessment of clothing on efficiency of employee productivity.

The simulation of thermophysiological behaviour of the human by using of a number of thermal manikins has a constant standing body posture on sweating thermal manikins [1]. For analysis of vibrations levels of personal equipment could be use systems such as motion capture [2] and wearable activity tracking [3].

Fig. 1. Wearable EDA sensors from: a - Xsens MVN - Inertial Motion Capture [2]; b - Wearable Activity Tracking in Car Manufacturing [3]; c - The SMASH system (inside layer) with Konnex and three Gateways [4]

Also the usage of warp knit mesh fabrics [5] that are widely used in different technical and medical purposes with conductive thread excludes presence of unstretchable wires in clothing systems.

Thus, the practical value of this research is components and new design development, as whole, functional clothing for special needs with integrated wireless sensor networks. The example of area-differentiated arrangement was introduced by author such as biometric complex [6] based on analysis of factors that influence on zonation, qualitative and quantitative composition of wireless sensor network elements and could be used for microclimate monitoring under clothing space.

Referencies

1. Wang F., Zhang C. Physiological Responses Predicted by Thermoregulatory Model Controlled Manikin: Does Simulation of Body Posture Make a

Difference? // Proceedings of the 11th International Meeting on Thermal Manikin and Modelling (11i3m). – 2016. – С. 70.

2. Roetenberg D., Luinge H., Slycke P. Xsens MVN: full 6DOF human motion tracking using miniature inertial sensors // Xsens Motion Technologies BV, Tech. Rep. – 2009.

3. Stiefmeier T. et al. Wearable activity tracking in car manufacturing // IEEE Pervasive Computing. – 2008. – Т. 7. – №. 2. – С. 42-50.

4. Harms H. et al. Rapid prototyping of smart garments for activity-aware applications // Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Smart Environments. – 2009. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 87-101.

5. Ermolenko I.V. A new aspect of use of warp-knitting meshy fabrics // Visnyk Hmel'nyc'kogo nacional'nogo universytetu. Serija: Tehnichni nauky. – 2013. – №. 3. – С. 74-78.

6. Kurhanskyi A. V., Zashhepkina N. M. Monitoryng aktyvnosti vodija iz zastosuvannjam bezdrotovyh sensoryh merezh // Visnyk Zhytomyrs'kogo derzhavnogo tehnologichnogo universytetu. Serija: Tehnichni nauky. – 2016. – №. 2 (77).